

CONSTRUCTION ON INTUITIONISTIC CYCLIC M-FUZZY GROUPS

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Abstract:

In this paper, the notion of cyclic group on a set is well-known. The study and extension of this classical notion of the M-fuzzy set to define concept of Intuitionistic Cyclic M-fuzzy group. By using this Intuitionistic Cyclic M-fuzzy group to investigate some results.

Key Words: M fuzzy sets, M- fuzzy groups, Cyclic M-fuzzy group, Intuitionistic Cyclic M-fuzzy groups.

1. Introduction:

After the introduction of the concept of fuzzy sets by L. A. Zadeh [7], researchers were conducted the generalizations of the notion of fuzzy sets, A. Rosenfeld [3] introduced the concept of fuzzy group and the idea of "Intuitionistic fuzzy set" was first published by K. T. Atanassov [1]. Jianming Zhan and Zhisong Tan [2] introduced the concept of "Intuitionistic M-fuzzy group" with operators. Dr. G. Subbiah[6] introduced the concept of "Cyclic M-fuzzy group" with sufficient conditions. In this paper, we give a sufficient condition for cyclic M fuzzy subgroup to be an Intuitionistic Cycle M-fuzzy group.

2. Preliminaries:

Definition 2.1: Let A and B be fuzzy sets. Then A is a subset of B if $\mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x)$ for every $x \in U$ and it is denoted by $A \subseteq B$ or $B \supseteq A$.

Definition 2.2: Two fuzzy sets A and B are called equal if $\mu_A(x) = \mu_B(x)$ for every $x \in U$ and it is denoted by $A = B$

Definition 2.3: Let A and B be fuzzy sets. Then the algebraic product of two fuzzy sets A and B is defined by $A \cdot B = \{ (x, \mu_{A \cdot B}(x)) / x \in U, \mu_{A \cdot B} = \mu_A \cdot \mu_B \}$

Definition 2.4: Let A and B be fuzzy sets. Then the Union $A \cup B$ and Intersection $A \cap B$ are respectively defined by the equations.

$$A \cup B = \{ (x, \mu_{A \cup B}(x)) / x \in U, \mu_{A \cup B}(x) = \max \{ (\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)) \}$$

$$A \cap B = \{ (x, \mu_{A \cap B}(x)) / x \in U, \mu_{A \cap B}(x) = \min \{ (\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)) \}$$

Remark 2.5: These definitions can be generated for countable number of fuzzy sets. If $\tilde{A}_1, \tilde{A}_2, \dots$, are fuzzy sets with membership functions $\mu_{\tilde{A}_1}(x), \mu_{\tilde{A}_2}(x), \dots$, then the membership functions of $X = \cup \tilde{A}_i$ and $Y = \cap \tilde{A}_i$ are defined as $\mu_x(x) = \max \{ \mu_{\tilde{A}_1}(x), \mu_{\tilde{A}_2}(x), \dots \}$ and $\mu_y(x) = \min \{ \mu_{\tilde{A}_1}(x), \mu_{\tilde{A}_2}(x), \dots \}$, $x \in U$ respectively.

Definition 2.6: A mapping $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$, where X is an arbitrary non-empty set and is called a fuzzy set in X.

Definition 2.7: Let M and G a set and a group respectively. A mapping $\mu : M \times G \rightarrow [0,1]$ is Called M-fuzzy sets in G. For any M-fuzzy set μ in G and $t \in [0,1]$ we define the set $U(\mu; t) = \{ X \in G / \mu(mx) \geq t, m \in M \}$ which is called an upper cut of 'μ' and can used to the characteristic of μ.

Definition 2.8: let f be a non- fuzzy function from X to Y .The image $f(\tilde{A})$ of a M-fuzzy set \tilde{A} on X is defined by means of the extension principle as

$$f(\tilde{A}) = \{ (my, \mu_{f(\tilde{A})}(my)) / y = f(x), x \in X \}$$

$$\text{Where } \mu_{f(\tilde{A})}(my) = \begin{cases} \text{Sup}\{ \mu_{\tilde{A}}(mx) \} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.9: A M- fuzzy set 'A' is called M- fuzzy group of G if

(MFG1) $A(mx, y) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$

(MFG2) $A(mx^{-1}) = A(x)$

(MFG3) $A(me) = 1$ for all $x, y \in G$ and $m \in M$.

Definition 2.10: let $G = \langle a \rangle$ be a cyclic group. If $\tilde{A} = \{ (a^n, \mu(a^n)) / n \in \mathbb{Z} \}$ is a fuzzy group, then \tilde{A} is called a cyclic fuzzy group generated by $(a, \mu(a))$ and denoted by $\langle a, \mu(a) \rangle$.

Definition 2.11: Let $A = \langle ma \rangle$ be a M- cyclic group. If $\tilde{A} = \{ (ma^n, \mu(ma^n)) / n \in \mathbb{Z} \}$ is a M- fuzzy group, then \tilde{A} is called a M- cyclic fuzzy group generated by $\langle (ma), \mu(ma) \rangle$.

3. Properties of M - Fuzzy Groups:

Proposition 3.1:

Let 'A' be a M- fuzzy group of G. Then (i) $A(mx) \leq A(me)$ for all $x \in G$ and $m \in M$.

(ii) The subset $G_A = \{ x \in G / A(mx) = A(me) \}$ is a M- fuzzy group of G.

Proof:

Let x be any element of G , then $A(mx, q) = \min \{ A(mx, q), A(mx, q) \}$
 $= \min \{ A(x), A(x^{-1}) \}$
 $\leq A(xx^{-1})$ since $A(e)=1$
 $= A(me)$ and (i) is proved.

To prove (ii) we have $e \in G_A$, then $G_A \neq \Phi$.

Now let $x, y \in G_A$ and $m \in M$.

$A(mxy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y^{-1}) \}$
 $= \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$
 $= \min \{ A(e), A(e) \}$
 $= A(e)$

but from (i) $A(mxy^{-1}) \leq A(e)$ for $x, y \in G$ and $m \in M$. Therefore $A(mxy^{-1}) = A(e)$

Which means $mxy^{-1} \in G_A$ and G_A is M -fuzzy group of G .

Corollary: let G be a finite group and A be a M -fuzzy group of G . Consider the subset H of G is given by $H = \{x \in G / A(mx) = A(e)\}$. Then H is a crisp subgroup of G .

Proposition 3.3:

A set of necessary and sufficient conditions for a M -fuzzy set of a group G to be a M -fuzzy group of G is that $A(mxy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$ for all x, y in G and m in M .

Proof:

Let A be a M -fuzzy group of G . Then

$A(mxy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y^{-1}) \}$
 $= \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$ for $x, y \in G$ and $m \in M$.

For the converse part suppose that A be M -fuzzy set of the group G of which e is the identity element.

Now $A(myy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ A(y), A(y) \}$
 $A(e)$ or $A(e) \geq A(y)$
 Now $A(mey^{-1}) \geq \min \{ A(e), A(y) \}$
 or $A(my^{-1}) \geq A(y)$
 Also $A(mxy) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y^{-1}) \}$
 $\geq \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$.

Hence the proof

4. Intuitionistic Cyclic M-Fuzzy Group:

Definition 4.1: Let $\tau = \langle ma \rangle$ be a M -cyclic group if $\tilde{\tau} = \{ \langle ma^n, \mu(ma^n), \vartheta(ma^n) \rangle | n \in \mathbb{Z} \}$ is the Intuitionistic Cyclic M -fuzzy group $\langle ma, \mu(ma^n), \vartheta(ma^n) \rangle$ Where $\mu(ma^n)$ is a membership function, $\vartheta(ma^n)$ is a non-membership function.

Theorem 4.2:

If G is a group, then prove that $\tilde{\tau}^m = \{ \langle ma^n, \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^n)^m, \vartheta_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^n)^m / n \in \mathbb{Z} \}$ is also a Intuitionistic Cycle M -fuzzy group.

Proof:

Let us show that $\tilde{\tau}^m$ satisfies three conditions (MFG1-MFG3) in definition (2.9). We can consider only its membership function because the m^{th} power of $\tilde{\tau}_m$ effects just only the membership function of $\tilde{\tau}_m$.

MFG1: Since τ is a M -fuzzy group and $\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma) \in [0, 1]$

$$\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}((ma^{n_1}), (ma^{n_2}))^m \geq \min \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^{n_1}), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^{n_2}) \}$$

$$= \min \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^{n_1})^m, \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^{n_2})^m \}$$

MFG2: $\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^n) = \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^{-n})$

Since $\tilde{\tau}$ is M -fuzzy group
 $\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^n)^m = (\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^{-n}))^m$

MFG3: $\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(me, q) = 1$

Since $\tilde{\tau}$ is M -fuzzy group
 Then $(\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(me, q))^m = 1$

Hence the proof.

Example 4.3:

Let τ be a M -Cyclic group with 12 elements and generated by (ma) . Let $\tilde{\tau}$ be a M -fuzzy set of the group τ defined as follows

$$\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^0) = 1$$

$$\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^4) = \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^8) = t_1,$$

$$\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^2) = \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^6) = \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^{10}) = t_2$$

And $\mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(mx) = t_3$ for all other elements X in τ

Where $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in [0,1]$ with $t_1 > t_2 > t_3$.

It is clear that $\tilde{\tau}$ is a M-fuzzy group of τ thus $\tilde{\tau} = \{(ma^k), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^k), \vartheta_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma^k)/k \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ is a Intuitionistic Cyclic M-fuzzy group generated by $((ma), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}}(ma))$.

Proposition 4.4:

If $\tilde{\tau}^i$ and $\tilde{\tau}^j$ are M-cyclic fuzzy groups then $\tilde{\tau}^i \cup \tilde{\tau}^j$ is also Intuitionistic Cycle M-fuzzy group if $i < j$.

Proof:

Since $i < j$ then we've $\mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i} > \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MFG1: } &= \max \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n a^m), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^n a^m) \} \\ &= \max \{ \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n a^m)^i, \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^n a^m)^j \} \} \\ &= \left(\mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n a^m) \right)^i \\ &> \min \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^m) \} \\ &> \min \left\{ \max \left\{ \left(\mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^m) \right) \right\}, \max \left\{ \left(\mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^m) \right) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \max \left\{ \left(\mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^n) \right) \right\}, \max \left\{ \left(\mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^m), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^m) \right) \right\} \right\} \\ &\geq \min \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i \cup \tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^n), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i \cup \tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^m) \} \end{aligned}$$

MFG1 is satisfied.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MFG2: } &\mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i \cup \tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^{-n}) \\ &= \max \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^{-n}), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^{-n}) \} \\ &= \max \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^{-n})^i, \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^{-n})^j \} \\ &= \max \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n)^i, \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^n)^j \} \\ &= \max \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(ma^n), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^n) \} \\ &= \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i} \cup \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(ma^n) \end{aligned}$$

MFG2 is satisfied

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MFG3: } &\mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i} \cup \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(me) \\ &= \max \{ \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^i}(me), \mu_{\tilde{\tau}^j}(me) \} \\ &= \max \{ 1, 1 \} = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\tilde{\tau}^i \cup \tilde{\tau}^j$ is Intuitionistic Cyclic M- fuzzy group.

Proposition 4.5:

If \tilde{A}_i and \tilde{A}_j are M-cyclic fuzzy groups then $\tilde{A}_i \cap \tilde{A}_j$ is also Intuitionistic cyclic M-fuzzy group

Proof:

This theorem may be proved similarly to proposition.4.4.

Remark:

Since a cyclic Intuitionistic M- fuzzy group is an abelian group , It is clear that $\mu(mxy) = \mu(myx)$ for $x, y \in A, m \in M$.

Conclusion:

In this paper, we extend Intuitionistic Cyclic M Fuzzy group to M Fuzzy set to define the concept of Cyclic M- fuzzy groups. We give a sufficient for M – Fuzzy subset to be Intuitionistic Cyclic M fuzzy group family and investigate its structure and properties with application.

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